

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: FAUST****FIRST NAME: INGA****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Deleted:

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2024 on Mac Version 16.90.2

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following best describes the purpose of a literature review in a dissertation?
 - To summarize all prior research on the topic
 - To critique and evaluate previous studies
 - To identify gaps in knowledge and justify the current study¹
 - To list all sources consulted for the research
2. What is the recommended way to introduce an unfamiliar abbreviation in EU documents?

¹ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 32-33.

Deleted: (Second Edition),

Formatted: Font: Not Italic

Formatted: Font: Not Italic, Superscript

Formatted: Font: Not Italic

Formatted: Justified

- Use the abbreviation immediately without explanation
 - Provide a glossary of abbreviations at the end of the document
 - Spell out the full term followed by the abbreviation in parentheses²**
 - Use the abbreviation and explain it in a footnote
3. What is the recommended way to form plurals of abbreviations in academic writing?
- Add an apostrophe and 's' (e.g. CPU's)
 - Add only 's' without an apostrophe (e.g. CPUs)³**
 - Use the same form for singular and plural
 - Spell out the full term in plural form
4. What is the main goal of using abbreviations in EU documents?
- To save space in the document
 - To demonstrate the writer's expertise
 - To improve reader comprehension⁴**
 - To adhere to formal writing conventions
5. What is the primary purpose of research, according to Turabian?
- To gather information

² European Union, *English Style Guide. A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* (European Union, 2021), 41–42.

³ [Ibid., 17.](#)

⁴ [Ibid., 41–42.](#)

Deleted: no. 8,

Deleted: European Union, *English Style Guide. A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission no. 8*, (European Union, 2021), 17.

Deleted: European Union, *English Style Guide. A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission no. 8*, (European Union, 2021), 41–42.

- To answer questions important to the researcher and community⁵**
- To improve writing skills
- To critique existing literature
6. Which of the following is NOT one of the main components of a dissertation process?
- Concept paper
- Prospectus
- Dissertation
- Peer review process⁶**
7. What is the recommended way to integrate quotations in academic writing?
- Always use block quotes for emphasis
- Avoid using quotations entirely
- Use quotations sparingly and integrate them into your writing⁷**
- Use as many quotations as possible to support your arguments
8. What is the primary purpose of building a storyboard in the research process?
- To create a visual representation of the research

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 139–140.

⁶ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University, 2024), 4.

⁷ Turabian, 75.

Deleted: no. 9

Formatted: Superscript

Formatted: Justified

Deleted: COURSEPACK (PERIOD 1)

Formatted: Superscript

Deleted: Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations no. 9*, (The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 75.

- To organize ideas and plan the research structure**⁸
- To present findings to the dissertation committee
- To outline the literature review
9. What is the recommended approach for revising a dissertation draft?
- Focus only on grammar and spelling
- Revise only the introduction and conclusion
- Start with the overall structure, then move to the details**⁹
- Have peers review it without personal revision
10. What is the key principle in ensuring alignment in qualitative dissertation research?
- Using only one type of data collection method
- Maintaining consistency across all components of the study**¹⁰
- Focusing solely on the research questions
- Avoiding any changes to the initial research design

⁸ Turabian, 32–33.

⁹ Cleenerwerck and Gulma, 11–12.

¹⁰ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation. A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019), 235–36.

Formatted: Indent: Left: 0.63 cm, Hanging: 0.63 cm, No bullets or numbering

Deleted: Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations no. 9*, (The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 32–33.

Deleted: Laurent Cleenerwerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK (PERIOD 1)*, (Euclid University, 2024)

Deleted: *F*

Formatted: Justified

Deleted: no. 4,

Deleted: Columbia University

Formatted: Font: Not Italic

Formatted: Font: Not Italic, Superscript

Formatted: Font: Not Italic

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation. A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.
- European Union. *English Style Guide. A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. European Union, 2021.
- Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 2nd ed. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. 9th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

Deleted: ,

Deleted: 2019.

Formatted: Space After: 6 pt

Deleted: F

Deleted: no. 4

Formatted: Superscript

Deleted: Columbia University.

Deleted: ,

Deleted: 2024.

Deleted: COURSEPACK (PERIOD 1).

Deleted: 2021.

Deleted: 2017.

Deleted: (Second Edition).

Formatted: Superscript

Deleted: 2018.

Deleted: no. 9.

Formatted: Superscript